

the untreated nursery but no viruliferous insects were found among 80 tested.

RTV infection at 14 DT did not vary greatly among treatments (see figure). At 33 DT, lower infection of RTBV + RTSV was found in plants treated at 2 and 16 DT and in plants treated in the nursery and at 2 and 16 DT.

More significant differences in infection were observed at 61 DT. Infection in plants treated at 2 and 16 DT and those treated in the nursery and at 2 and 16 DT did not differ.

Insecticides applied during the first 2 wk after transplanting slowed RTV development, resulting in a lower level of infection even 61 DT. Insecticide application in nurseries may not be economical because there was no appreciable difference in infection between untreated seedlings and those treated in the nursery. ■

Infection of RTBV and RTSV assayed by ELISA in IR22 plants at different days after transplanting after insecticide treatments in the nursery, and at 2 and 16 DT. IRRI, 1990.

Effect of wet-dry cycles on sclerotial weight and viability of *Sclerotium hydrophilum*

S. Sunder, D. S. Dodan, S. C. Ahuja, and A. Singh, Haryana Agricultural University, Rice Research Station, Kaul 132021, Haryana, India

Sclerotium hydrophilum Sacc. causes rice stem rot. The fungus survives through sclerotia, which are subjected to different field conditions. We studied the effect of alternate wet-dry cycles on sclerotial weight and viability.

Sclerotia produced on rice grain-hull medium were separated, washed, and their surface water absorbed with blotters. The moisture content of the freshly harvested sclerotia was 20.5%.

These sclerotia were dried in the shade at room temperature (26-37 °C) for 24 h. Their moisture content was reduced to 11.7%.

Six dishes containing 1,000 mg dried sclerotia each were wet for 24 h by adding 20 ml water to each dish. Then they were dried in shade for 24 h, for each wet-dry cycle. One set of six dishes was given no treatment. Three dishes in each set were used to measure weight, and three to measure viability.

1. Effect of wet-dry cycles (WD) on sclerotial weight in *Sclerotium hydrophilum*.

Sclerotia weight and viability of both treated and untreated sets were measured after each wet-dry cycle. For viability, sclerotia were surface sterilized with 0.05% H₂OCl₂, plated on 2% water-agar amended with 1,000 ppm streptomycin, and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C for 3 d. The wet-dry cycles continued until scler-

rotial weight became constant. After the last cycle, moisture content of untreated sclerotia was 11.3%; that of sclerotia subjected to wet-dry treatment was 11.5%.

At first, sclerotia weight was reduced sharply with wet-dry treatment to about half (490 mg) by completion of the third

cycle (Fig. 1). Weight stabilized after 11 cycles (428 mg).

Sclerotia viability declined gradually with wet-dry cycles, to 37% after 12 cycles (Fig. 2).

Without wet-dry cycles, sclerotia weight and viability remained constant.

The correlations between wet-dry cycle and weight ($r = -0.74$) and viability were negative ($r = -0.99$); that between weight and viability, positive ($r = 0.78$). ■

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

2. Effect of wet-dry cycles on sclerotial viability in *Sclerotium hydrophilum*.

Natural conidia release patterns of *Pyricularia oryzae*

Chang Kyu Kim and Hong Sik Min. Plant Pathology Department, Agricultural Sciences Institute, Suweon 440-707, Korea; and Reiichi Yoshino, Paddy Crop Disease Laboratory, National Agriculture Research Center, Tsukuba 305, Japan

We studied successive conidia release patterns for 48 h from discrete blast lesions—3, 7, and 4 d old—19-21 Jul 1989 in Korea, using a KY-type spore trap. The weather was continuously cloudy during the experiment.

Preexisting conidia and conidiophores were brushed away with moistened cotton and the spore trap set up. On day 1, conidia release from 3-d-old lesions peaked three times, at 0100, 0500, and 0900 h (see figure). From 7-d-old lesions, conidia release peaked at 0700 h. From 4-d-old lesions, conidia release peaked at 0300 and 0700 h.

On day 2, mostly two peaks occurred 0100 and 0500 h; after rainfall, two extra peaks occurred from 3-d-old

Successive *Pyricularia oryzae* conidia release pattern from three different types of leaf BI lesions. Icheon, Korea, 1989.

lesions, at 0900 and 1300 h. The total amount of conidia released was higher on day 2.

In general, conidia release peaked between 0100-0700 h. The reason 3-d-old lesions exhibited the highest release peak later than other lesions is not yet clear.

We do see that the BI fungus cycle is repeated diurnally, except with daytime rainfall.

Such quantitative measurements will be useful in simulation modeling for leaf BI forecasting. ■